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Abstract

The term "cohesion" is of Latin origin and means "connected, stuck together" In scientific literature, this term is used in the sense of the bonding, sticking together of molecules (atoms) of a substance under the influence of attractive forces (intermolecular interaction forces, hydrogen bond forces, chemical interaction forces). These forces determine the physical and physicochemical properties of a substance, its aggregate state, volatility, solubility, mechanical properties, etc. In linguistics, cohesion is considered a set of means that connect the components of a text. English linguists M. Halliday and R. Hasan defined cohesion in their work "Cohesion in English" as follows: "Cohesion is a set of meaningful connections that are common to all texts and play the role of a means of revealing the mutual relationship of the content of individual parts" [1]. Cohesion reveals not what information the text provides, but how the meaning integrity of the text is organized. The analysis of any text, whether scientific, artistic, or journalistic, shows that its components are connected to each other by a number of means, turning into a single speech act, ensuring the sequence of events and facts in it. Then a whole text is created in which there is some sequence, connection between the described events, and various means between sentences serve this connection. When analyzing any text, it is also observed that its parts, which are located quite far from each other, form a connection with each other to one degree or another, and these means of connection do not always correspond to traditional grammatical means. That is, in addition to connectors, verb-adjective compounds, in a word, various grammatical forms, other means are also involved in the organization of the text: logical, associative, composition-structural, stylistic, rhythmic (melodic, tonal, etc.) means. Such means of communication have recently been combined under the term "cohesion". Taking into account these aspects [1]. Cohesion in the sense of Galperin is a special type of connection that ensures the interdependence, sequence (continuum) of individual information, facts, events [21].

Keywords: Cohesion, grammatical means, formal communication means, the means of connection of components, stylistic methods, logical connections, syntactic whole.

Introduction:

V. Vinogradov also indicated three means that organize the text: intonation, word order and explicit signs of the text - demonstrative pronouns, conjunctions, articles, etc. [2]. A. Kehler defined the three means in a slightly different plan.

1) formal-grammatical (prepositions, conjunctions); 2) deictic (articles, personal and demonstrative pronouns, the words there, how, then, the former, the latter); syntactic means [1]. M. Halliday and R. Hasan generally called the means involved in the structural-semantic organization of the text "cohesion" [3]. Prosodic means include the tonality of the sentence in the speech process, rhythmic-melodic flow, intonation, pause, stress, etc. Morphological means include a number of main parts of speech (especially pronouns) and auxiliary parts of speech. Syntactic means that connect the components of the text are distinguished by their diversity. These means include word order, repetitions, parallelism, etc. [3]. S. Lyons identifies 6 types of means in the structural-semantic structure of the text in English and Azerbaijani linguistics under the name of formal communication means. [6].

1) phonetic repetition (this includes artistic stylistic methods such as alliteration, assonance); 2) morphological repetition (repetition of signs of the categories of gender, tense, case); 3) lexical repetition (complete, incomplete, i.e. repetition of words in various grammatical forms and zero repetition), 4) syntactic repetition (complete and incomplete repetition of word order, chiasm, etc.); 5) lexical-grammatical means (connectors, prepositions, determinants, etc.); 6) deictic elements (pronouns of various types, articles, etc. [4]. C. Schaar

in her monograph "Text syntax" describes the text components dividing the connecting means into three parts, he named them as follows: lexical means (words-forms, lexical repetitions, use of homonyms, etc.), morphological means (connectors and connecting words, adats, modal words, etc.), syntactic means (word order, sentence structure, syntactic repetitions, synonymy-parallelism) [7]. Although this division is based more on Azerbaijani language materials, in our opinion, it is the most convenient division in the study of literary texts.

Both syntactic and logical connections play a key role in the structural-semantic organization of the text. The essence of syntactic connection is characterized by the means we listed above. There are two types of logical connection: chain and parallel connection. In chain connection, the rhyme of the preceding sentence acts as the theme of the following ones, and this relationship continues throughout the text. In texts with parallel connection, the rhyme of one sentence does not relate to the other. First comes the generalizing sentence, then its content is interpreted in parallel in other sentences. Anaphora and epiphora are widely used in such texts.

As can be seen from the summary of the scientific literature and our observations on various texts, the means connecting the components of the text are extremely rich and diverse. Let us consider the role of cohesion, which is a set of these means, in English and Azerbaijani texts. The story *Animal Farm* by the English writer G. Orwell attracts attention in this regard. The second chapter of the work consists of several syntactic wholes that are interconnected. Based on them, the characteristics of the means of cohesion are clearly visible. The first syntactic whole consists of two sentences.

"Three nights later old Major died peacefully in his sleep. His body was buried at the foot of the orchard (G. Orwell. "Animal Farm", p.6) [5].

The connection between these sentences was realized by replacing the proper noun Major with the possessive pronoun his and the metonymic noun body. In addition, textual synonyms such as died, was buried also participated in this connection. The second syntactic whole begins with these words:

This was early in March. (G.Orwell, "Animal Farm", p.6) [5].

Here the demonstrative pronoun this plays the role of a grammatical means between syntactic wholes. Then:

"During the next three months there was much secret activity. (G.Orwell, "Animal Farm.p.6) [5].

The combinations early in March and during the next three months in the sentences act as time parameters of the information and logically connect the described events to each other. In addition, cohesion in this syntactic whole is realized through the main word combination secret activity.

"Major's speech had given to the more intelligent animals on the farm a completely new outlook on life. They did not know when the Rebellion predicted by the Major would take place, they had no reason for thinking that it would be within their own lifetime, but saw clearly that it was their duty to prepare for it" [G. Orwell, "Animal Farm", p.6] [5].

The connection between these sentences is the lexical repetition of the proper noun Major and the pronoun they, as well as the pronoun they of the combination the more intelligent animals, the noun the Rebellion with the pronoun it The following syntactic whole draws the reader's attention by conveying the image.

The work of teaching and organizing the others fell naturally upon pigs, who were generally recognized as being the cleverest of the animals. Pre-eminent among the pigs were two young boars named Snowball and Napoleon, whom Mr. Jones was breeding up for sale (G.Orwell, "Animal Farm", p.6) [5].

Here cohesion occurs through lexical repetition of the nouns the pigs, the animals, the boars and substitution with the pronouns the pigs-who, the boars-whom. Then the following is read:

"Napoleon was a large, rather fierce-looking Berkshire boar, the only Berkshire on the farm, not much of a talker, but with a reputation for getting his own way Snowball was a more vivacious pig than Napoleon, quicker in speech and more eventive, but was not considered to have the same depth of character. (G.Orwell, "Animal Farm", p.6) [5]. Cohesion within this syntactic whole, as well as with its previous syntactic whole, is created by the lexical repetition of the proper nouns Snowball, Napoleon. The next syntactic whole consists of the description of the Reporter. The sentences here are connected by the lexical repetition of the noun pigs:

"All the other male pigs on the farm were porkers. The best known among them was a small fat pig named Squealer, with very round cheeks, thinking eyes, nimble movements, and a shrill voice. He was a brilliant talker, and when he was arguing some difficult point he had a way of skipping from side to side and whisking his tail which was somehow persuasive. The others said

of Squealer that he could turn black into white. (G.Orwell, "Animal Farm", p.6) [5]

These sentences are formed by the following pronouns (Squealer is replaced by the personal pronoun he, porkers by the personal pronoun them), the grammatical substitute form he is replaced by his, the repetition of the pronoun he is formed by the lexical repetition of the proper noun Squealer.

The next syntactic whole begins with these words:

These three had elaborated old Major's teachings into a complete system of thought, to which they gave the name of Animalism

(G.Orwell, "Animal Farm", p.6) [5].

Here, by replacing the proper nouns Napoleon, Snowball, Squealer with the previous syntactic whole, the connection with the previous one was sought. In addition, the word teaching, although located at a distance, acted as a lexical repetition in the whole text, which also served to implement cohesion.

Aim:

Let us also pay attention to other grammatical cohesion tools in this work:

"In a very little while the animals had destroyed everything that reminded them of Mr. Jones. Napoleon then led them back to the storehouse and served out a double ration of corn to everybody, with two biscuits for each dog. Then they sang "Beasts of England" from end to end seven times running, and after that they settled down for the night and slept as they had never slept before." (G. Orwell. "Animal Farm", p.8) [5]. This syntactic whole includes 3 sentences. The author used the following cohesion tools here: time units connecting separate events such as in a very little while, then, after that, replacement of the noun the animals with them, repetition of the pronoun they. This syntactic whole is connected with the next syntactic whole by the conjunction but:

"But they worked as usual, and suddenly remembering the glorious thing that had happened, they all raced out into the pasture together. (G.Orwell, "Animal Farm", p.8) [5].

Syntactic parallelism played a major role in the combination of the components of this syntactic whole, the first sentence of which we have given.

The syntactic wholes in G. Orwell's story "Animal Farm" are implemented not only by formal-grammatical means of cohesion, but also by unconventional grammatical means. Here, the logical means of cohesion are also clearly felt. In linguistic literature, logical connection is also called temporal mutual relation In the work we are considering, the temporal parameters of the event as a means of cohesion are sufficient: three nights later, during the next three months, after Mr. Jones was asleep, now, in past year, on Midsummer's Eve, when, the next moment, after only a moment or two, a minute later, for the first few minutes, then, in a very little while, after a moment, after this, after a little thought, soon, in a few minutes, etc. In this passage, the role of lexical units with temporal semantics in the formation of cohesion is clearly visible. Thus, temporal words and their functional-stylistic equivalents give simultaneity to the events described in the flow of speech in relation to each other. Temporal words, by

expressing the concept of time, unite sentences with a single meaning and structure [9].

In the work, we also observe the spatial parameters of information as a logical type of cohesion in the formation of syntactic wholes: round the boundaries of the farm, back to the farm buildings, outside the door, the top bar of the gate. Since the work is built on the basis of a narrative from beginning to end, the temporal and spatial parameters of information, connecting separate events, give them authenticity. Logical cohesion ensures the semantic-logical sequence of the text, the gradual unfolding of its content, thematic-rhematic relationships [7].

One of the unconventional grammatical means of cohesion is associative cohesion. Other aspects of the structure of the text, associative cohesion, are reimpectic, connotative, subjective modality. This type of cohesion is not as clearly observed as other means [10]. As C. Schaar noted, associativity can also be called a hidden connection, since in some texts type b of cohesion exists not openly, but secretly [7].

Research methodology:

One type of associative cohesion is allusion (hint). The term allusion is understood as a stylistic form that refers to real facts, historical events, literary works known to everyone [10]. G. Orwell's "Animal Farm" is entirely based on allusion, that is, this story creates associations with historical events in the reader [5]. Indeed, if there is no association between G.Orwell's difficult life and the known real facts about the Russian Revolution, it is impossible to understand the pragmatic purpose of this work. In this work, the associative form of connection is created by figurative cohesion. The author has connected not real objects, but images that embody historical events. In this sense, the image of Napoleon in the work attracts attention. With this image, the author depicted any tyrant, in particular, Stalin. Proof of this is Napoleon's not only his tyrannical and domineering nature, but also his actions. For example, Napoleon forces animals that threaten his absolute power to confess to actions they have never committed, and such confessions end in death:

"Then a goose came forward and confessed to having secreted and eaten them in the night... And so the tale of confessions and executions went on until there was a pile of corpses lying before Napoleon's feet and the air was heavy with the smell of blood... ("G. Orwell, "Animal Farm", p.27) [5].

In fact, these events really happened in history: the 1930s are associated with secret arrests, interrogations, etc. Napoleon was afraid of assassination, so he was always surrounded by his loyal dogs. In addition, a young boar tasted his food to check if it was poisonous. Another interesting fact is that Napoleon himself was awarded medals:

"Napoleon emerged from the farmhouse, wearing both his medals (for he had recently awarded himself "Animal Hero, First Class," and "Animal Hero, Second Class" ("G. Orwell, "Animal Farm", p.27) [5].

His loyal student, the informer, played a significant role in the formation and development of Napoleon's image. The informer created the image of a great leader by exaggerating Napoleon's capabilities and giving him various titles. The animals who listened to

these eloquent speeches of the informer believed in Napoleon's greatness. "Under the guidance of our Leader, Comrade Napoleon, I have laid five eggs in six days" etc.

The analysis of the means of cohesion in G. Orwell's "Animal Farm" can be summarized as follows:

1. Traditional grammatical means:

- a) lexical repetitions - the animals, Napoleon;
- b) the use of pronouns repetition-they, he, their;
- c) expression with pronouns-the pigs-they, Mollie-she, the Rebellion-it;

d) connection based on synonyms-pigs-boars-porkers;

d) connectors-and, but;

2. Non-traditional grammatical means:

a. Logical cohesion:

1) time parameters of information: three nights later, during the next three months, after only a moment or two, on Midsummer's Eve;

2) spatial parameters of information:

round the boundaries of the farm, outside the door, the top bar of the gate.

b. Associative cohesion.

c. Figurative cohesion.

Now, for comparison, let us pay attention to the cohesion means in the works of the outstanding classical poet of Azerbaijan, Shah Ismail Khatai:

My heart is broken in the grave, my smiling friend.

My dear, let me search your heart, see how many evils there are in it.

Don't come near me, oh friend of the Hijri-tongue.

The enemy's friend cries bitterly for me.

The nightingale cries bitterly for the rose-faced bird-soul.

You have made me live with the cycle of life.

My life trembles without you, oh my language.

How can the language be calm, the expectation has exceeded the limit. I am waiting for the promise-event every time.

I have always been crazy, I have fallen into the mountains alone, undecided.

I have become undecided, apart from the only hairs of my hair.

"In the darkness, the trees, as if holding hands, had moved forward from all sides, narrowing the circle of the prey: when you look from the acacia grove, the space ahead seemed to be the size of a threshing floor. The leveling and leveling of the foresters' hearths under low sheds seemed to have become even flatter in the evening darkness, almost level with the ground. And the slates of the Finnish house at the top, wet from the evening dew, were turning white under the stars" (Isa Huseynov "Tragedy")

One of the unconventional means of cohesion is formal cohesion. Formal cohesion is manifested not only between the components of the text, but also between words and word combinations in a simple sentence, and between the constituent parts of a complex sentence [7]. In the following text, we see that formal cohesion is established in this way.

"There were two things left from Rahman and Bahman. One was the iron they once wore around their waists like belts in the square in front of the office. The

other was Bahman's shirmayil saz, which the Isfandiyar man, for some reason, distinguished from Rahman and cherished as "the last cradle - the guardian of my homeland" (Isa Huseynov, "Saz").

Formal cohesion in this text served to create a syntactic whole through various formal means ("one", "the other").

The examples we have given from works written in English and Azerbaijani show that the phenomenon of cohesion, which is an important means of creating a text, manifests itself as a linguistic universality. The analysis of the phenomenon of cohesion in both languages shows that traditional grammatical (lexical repetitions, substitutions with pronouns, conjunctions) and non-traditional grammatical means (logical, associative, formal) are characteristic of cohesion in both English and Azerbaijani.

A text is a speech act that helps to carry out verbal communication. A text is created when each speaking individual selects language units in accordance with his communicative goals and combines them with the grammatical rules of his language. The ideas of the English linguist Z. S. Harris [9] attract attention in terms of determining other features of the text. Speech does not consist of separate words and sentences, but consists of a single-word sentence, from a monologue to ten-volume works, to entire discussions [9]. The construction of the speech process and the perception of what is said are carried out on the basis of both intralinguistic and extralinguistic factors. However, it should also be taken into account that a text is not just a collection of separate phrases. Since a text is a complete language unit with a complex structure and content, its communicative material also arises from the sum of these two aspects.

The content structure of a text appears in three perspectives: vertical, horizontal and theme-rheme structure. The vertical structure of a text is determined by its formal-thematic content; this content arises in the general meaning of the text, which is connected in the smallest details of the text - subtheme, subsubtheme, microtheme and separate considerations. Such a top-down arrangement is carried out by the speaking individual who creates a text in accordance with his communicative goals. The recipient of the text, the perceiver forms this hierarchical structure in the opposite direction from bottom to top, while the process of understanding the content as a whole is implemented from the smallest parts. The vertical structure of the text is not always built correctly and logically - some microthemes are omitted, others can enter into "alien" subthemes, act as a reflection of each other, etc. Such an imperfect expression of thought is eliminated by the communicator's (listener's) awareness of the final content of the entire text, or on the basis of his experience and a certain level. In addition, individual fragments of the text allow us to foresee subsequent events. Such "foresights" greatly facilitate the comprehension of speech. [10].

Its horizontal structure plays an important role in the formation of the integrity of the text. This structural form provides formal and semantic relationships between individual phrases. As we noted in the previous sections, the formal cohesion of the text (cohesion) is

realized by various linguistic means (connectors, repetitions, pronouns, time agreements, etc.). The semantic integrity (coherence) of the text is ensured by logical sequence, non-contradiction of considerations, logical connections ("thus", "thus", "therefore", "finally", etc.), stereotyped formals indicating the beginning and end of the narrative. Anaphoric and cataphoric means, etc.

The coherence of the text is directly related to its theme-rheme structure. Theme and rheme relations, or actual membership, are also characteristic of the content structure of the utterance. Violation of the sequence in the theme-rheme chain and the replacement of the microtheme (which in many cases occur simultaneously) determine the boundaries of phraseological wholes [12]. Two meaning focuses can be noted in the content of the utterance. One of them (theme) is the initial, starting point for the information about what is being talked about, assumed, and whether the interlocutor is a Kabari (or not). The second (rhema) is the main meaning center that arises for the provision of information. The theme-rhema structure of the discourse can be implemented by emphasizing and selecting the rheme through intonation, lexical, or syntactic means. For example, the rheme of "lack of money" can be expressed in various ways. For example, by emphasis (he has no money), by lexical means (Money? He doesn't even have a penny), by syntactically placing the rheme at the end of a simple sentence (He has no money). The sequence in the text and the relationship between sentences depend greatly on the theme-rhema relationships of neighboring sentences. In many cases, the rheme of one sentence becomes the theme of another sentence:

Jahandar agha galloped his horse. The horse did not move (I. Shikhli, "Deli Kur").

In addition, a certain theme-rhema structure can appear in the content of the entire text, in which case the information in one part of the text is transferred to another part of the text. The starting point for the content in the part can play the role of the initial material (theme). Therefore, the theme realizes the relationship between the sentences of the text. Thus, a certain part of the text becomes the part that reveals the meaning. This part is the path to certainty, this path realizes the text [12].

These means that realize the text belong to the concrete-contextual aspects of speech, and although these features cover both artistic, scientific and journalistic texts to one degree or another, they serve more to create artistic texts. Because artistic texts have a specific communicative function and must have structural-semantic aspects corresponding to this. Each artistic text is a source of information that sets certain practical goals. When a writer provides information about something, he influences the reader. The strength of this influence depends on the descriptive-expressive texture of the artistic work. The comprehension of the artistic text as a whole and comprehensively depends on its understanding. Correct understanding of the artistic text can only occur if allows the author to use language units figuratively and express the issues that make the reader think with various means of a specific language.

A literary text has a number of differences in the use of language units in the structural-semantic plan

from other texts (which we conditionally call neutral texts). This is natural, because a literary text simultaneously performs communicative, expressive and aesthetic functions.

A neutral text written in any language is a kind of abstract object from a linguistic point of view, since the structure of its individual parts is diverse. The language of a neutral text is limited to trivial considerations inherent in short news items in newspapers, telegrams, articles of the Criminal Code. For example, the functional characteristic of a text is determined only by its communicativeness, which is a certain organized and directed information purpose. Its structural characteristic is determined by the provision of information. The semantic characteristic of a neutral text is determined by its coherence, that is, the interconnectedness of information. Neutral texts can be characterized at different levels of the language as follows [14]:

a) the phonetic aspect of a neutral text is mainly characterized by its lack of rhythmic regularity, the sequence of phonemes is perceived by communicants (the speaker and the listener) without any regularity;

b) in most cases, the repetition of elements in the morphological and lexical structure of a neutral text is not observed. Each morpheme or lexeme does not form a correspondence with the units preceding and following it, their location in the text has a chaotic effect from a stylistic point of view (although the regularity here is at a statistical level, it has no significance for communicants);

c) in the syntactic aspect of a neutral text, it is observed that the structure of independent sentences is not conditioned by the structure of the sentences surrounding it, that is, there is no structural-semantic connection between these components;

d) since there is no contextual content in a neutral text, their content-conceptual information can be realized.

The literary text is stylistically significant because the features of the neutral text model shown above are violated, a certain intensity is created in the text structure, and stylistic figures, figurative expression of thought come to the fore. In this sense, literary texts can be characterized at different levels of the language as follows:

a) in the literary text, at the phonetic level, attention is drawn to these aspects: the regularity of the rhythm of the text (especially the poetic text), alliteration, assonance and especially rhyme in the plan of the phonemic composition of the text, the regularity of various phonetic rules, suprasegmental and linear rules. For example, let's look at the following example from W. Shakespeare's sonnets. And simple truth miscall'd simplicity.

And captive good attending captain fill (W. Shakespeare, Sonnet 66) The regularity of the s sound in the words simple, simplicity, and the k sound in the words captive and captain in the example created the conditions for the emergence of a pun.

b) The syntagmatic repetition of morphemes and lexemes in a literary text is of great importance. A repeated morpheme or lexeme is considered either a stylistic defect or, as a rule, an effective stylistic device. A text acquires a stylistic quality when regularity in its

structure is realized by language units [9]. Lexical repetitions are observed more often in poetic texts. In prose works, repetition is usually carried out in the first sentence, the absence of repetition in subsequent sentences is a constructive feature of the syntactic whole, it is of great stylistic importance, in this case, by giving less space to words, a wide opportunity for meaning is created.

c) The syntactic aspect of a literary text is characterized by the following: stylistic repetition of sentence structures (parallelism); the interaction of mixed-type structures and their sequential repetition; regular replacement of sentence types, for example, interrogative sentences with narrative sentences. As a result of this, neutral texts turn into a type of literary texts, into dialogues.

All these phenomena we have considered are included in the list of traditional grammatical means. They can be included in the text without taking into account the meaning of certain language units. From a semantic point of view, a number of peculiarities are also observed in the construction of neutral and literary texts. In a neutral text, we usually do not encounter regular distributions of meaning types and textual units of the units that make up the text, or their mutual processing. Each element (lexical unit) differs from the element preceding or following it not only in terms of its specific lexical meaning, but also in terms of its type of meaning. Objects (events, processes) usually have a name accepted by everyone, any object is attributed to a certain sign according to its objective sign and is therefore named, but since there is a naming condition, a specific object can also be used in a sense that is not specific to it, depending on the communication conditions, this happens depending on the purpose of the communicants. In a literary text, this or that language identification can act in any functional position in different conditions and in the language of different characters. Therefore, there are specific aspects of the semasiological problematic of a literary text. If the connotative system is brought to the fore at the phonetic, morphological, lexical and syntactic levels, then the semantic structure of the literary text requires a different analysis of the utterance in the subject-logical plan. That is, the contextual structure of the utterance (syntactic whole) is brought to the fore [18].

Contextualization of speech is the basis of speech communication. It is the main condition for the means of communication between communicants. Adapting language units to a specific situation is a feature inherent in all language speakers. Because the specific-contextual meaning of the utterance and the text as a whole depends on individual knowledge, emotions and associations of the communicator and is not at the same level for everyone. The full assimilation of the entire content of a literary text does not depend only on the content and specific-contextual meaning. The ability to give additional meaning to the content of the text is also no less important in speech communication. This meaning appears implicitly. "The term implication is taken from the science of logic and is used in the sense of "to imply". The implicit meaning of a literary text is understood as the imagination and intention of an event or concept that is not mentioned or specifically described

in that text. Such means are used quite regularly in the language of literary works. This appears as a manifestation of the internal potential capabilities of the language, because the language mechanism is structured in such a way that, along with independent naming and direct means of designation, a whole system of indirect forms of expression and figurative expressions is involved in "active" activity. The artistic poetic structure of the language, its amazing richness and diversity are precisely so multi-layered, multifaceted. arises from a complex synthesis of means of communication and influence. In the construction of a literary text, along with the known metaphor of the word, the metaphor of the whole sentence also plays an important role. [15].

When talking about the implicit meaning of a literary text, the relationship between two informative complexes is meant: one of them is expressed directly by language means ("antecedent"), and the other ("consequent") appears through the first. Therefore, the plan of expression and the content plan of a linguistic sign can be evaluated as two objects in connection with the relationship of implication. A linguistic sign does not mean the implicit meaning of the text, since it is expressed directly by pronunciation or is not revealed by another intermediate informative complex. The implicit meaning differs from the allusion precisely because in the allusion, not another idea, the intended idea, but a two-way speech unit is reflected.

The study of the implicit meaning of a literary text has been carried out in two directions. On the one hand, cases of text implication have been studied within the framework of text linguistics. On the other hand, implicit elements in the semantic system of lexical units have been studied. The study of the implication of a literary text is related to philological or literary analysis. Here, primarily, works of art (literary texts) occupy a central place. A literary work, as a rule, is multi-planar, in addition to the external plot narrative, it has additional meaning planes, consequences derived from the main content. If we approach it from the point of view of content-conceptual information, for example, N. Enkwist, "Metamorphosis" at first glance causes disgust in the reader, but a more attentive reader can understand that this is not a story about the fate of a person turned into an insect, but an allusion. Enkwist, N wants to draw attention to the loneliness of a person in the family and society, to the indifference of people. All those who surround Gregor are his scoundrels who exploit him, they see him from the inside. Any desire for protection from betrayal, cruelty and meanness is embodied in his armored sheath. This sheath seems strong and reliable at first, but at the last moment it turns into a weak and fragile being, like Gregor's soul and human body. The real meaning of the comparison, analogy (parable) is precisely in this, the encounter between Gregor-man and Gregor-insect. Gregor, like any other person, is lonely. There are many reasons for such loneliness: incomprehensibility, inability to share someone else's pain, false feelings towards others, etc. A person burdened with everyday worries often does not notice those around him. He is content with them, does not try to change his life, acts in accordance with the paradoxical laws of life, as a result, a person loses himself. It is

impossible to live by subordinating himself to the interests of others. This is also confirmed [7]. N. Enkwist work the metamorphosis. That work indicates the inevitability of human loneliness in the current world conditions. [16].

There are many examples of the implicit meaning of a literary text in world literature. The work *The Storm Bird* (M. Gorky) is not just a description of a bird in a storm, but a passionate call to revolutionary struggle. The novel *Crime and Punishment* (F.M. Dostoevsky) is not only about the murder of a loan shark, but is actually an exposure of the murderer.

The implied meaning is often the most important goal of works of fiction, reflecting the author's intention, the main reason for writing the topic. Such implications arise both from the overall content of the text and from its individual parts, episodes, paragraphs.

In any case, such implications are not directly presented to the communicator, since this additional meaning is sometimes interpreted in different ways, it is not always easy to understand it.

The implication of a literary text occurs at a greater semantic depth, and its understanding requires not only knowledge of the language, but also analytical thinking, emotional sensitivity and artistic understanding. Finally, the informativeness in the semantic structure of a literary text is manifested in three aspects: content-factual, content-conceptual and content-subtext (subtext). The content-factual aspect of a literary text provides information about events and persons: such as the rebellion of animals on the farm in G. Orwell's "Animal Farm", the transformation of a person into an insect in "Metamorphosis". However, the analysis of the content-conceptual and content-subtext (subtext) aspects allows us to understand that these works are allusive in nature, based on a simile (parable): "In the work *Animal Farm*, animals are set against people, compared with them and likened to them. In the work "Metamorphosis", Gregor-man is compared with Gregor-insect. In both cases, the comparison is based on the opposition of human qualities such as generosity and kindness, and evil. Thus, the conceptual and content-subtext (textual) aspects of the text made it possible to reveal the wisdom, implicit semantics of this basis. Each work is built on the basis of narrative episodes. The basis of the narrative, as is known, is action verbs.

Since the literary text is a purposefully operated creative process, it obeys its own structural rules. Therefore, it can be assumed that individual parts, as well as the text as a whole, have mutually dependent features and categories. The relationship of these categories operates in different genres and different styles in a unique way. L.R. Galperin divides the categories of the text into two types: semantic and structural categories. In his opinion, informativeness, depth, presupposition and pragmatics belong to semantic categories, and integration, cohesion, retrospection, prospection, scoreness and continuum to structural categories [17] All of these categories have forms of self-realization. For example, as we have shown in the previous sections, the category of cohesion is a set of means that connect significantly distant components of the text with each other, the category of informativeness appears as a means of narration, description of conditions,

action, situation, nature, characters, judgment, etc. The category of retrospection manifests itself in both compositional and lexical means.

In fact, all categories of the text are facultatively, strongly interconnected, mutually condition each other. In this respect, the categories of cohesion and integration are closer to each other. Because integration can be realized in a number of cases by means of cohesion. Even in certain types of texts, cohesion provides integration. Integration (from Latin "construction, completion") is a concept in systems theory about the combination of separate parts into a whole [9]. In text linguistics, it is considered as the combination of separate components to complete the text. The category of integration of the text is realized by the following means, in the form of subordination of one part of the text to another, in the forms of consistent and inconsistent (this feature applies to sentences) forms of subordination, with stylistic devices: synonymous repetitions, etc.

I.R.Galperin also evaluates retrospection as a means of integration. Retrospection, as an important category of the text, creates conditions for its integration, determines the semantic and structural completion of the text [9]. Integration, by combining the meanings of separate syntactic wholes in the text, the content of separate chapters and sections, eliminates the independence of these parts, subordinates them to a single idea, to the result arising from the work. In fact, text integration is a process. Therefore P.R.Galperin characterized integration from three aspects:

- 1) integration as a process;
- 2) integration as a product, result of this process flow;

- 3) integration as a specific aspect of the text. Assessing integration as a process means studying the relationships between individual text units. Examining the result of this process requires considering the text as a whole. Studying integration as a specific, special aspect of the text is understood as studying the grammatical categories of the text [15].

The combination of parts of the text is a continuous process. This process continues until the text becomes whole. When we say the integrity of the text, we mean both its grammatical and semantic integrity. The semantic integrity of the text is the main thing, and integration ensures the semantic unity of the text. Integration manifests itself both in small texts, in syntactic wholes, and in large texts. However, integration in small texts differs from integration in large texts. To clarify this difference, it is necessary to pay attention to the level of completeness of information in small and large texts. In syntactic wholes, information is incomplete. More precisely, in such texts, information is incomplete. That is, the circle is not completely closed, on the one hand, it remains open from the right end, and in subsequent texts this gap is filled, the circle is closed, the idea is completed. In large texts, integration is already in a completed form. Here, the semantic load of the text is complete, and the text is closed from both sides [7].

Integration ensures the sequential tracing of the meaning of content-factual information. Integration is perceived in various ways both in artistic texts, and in

scientific, journalistic, and business texts. This category depends on the volume and size of the text. If the speaker's (writer's) goal is to provide the listener (reader) with certain information, on the other hand, the reader's (listener's) degree of understanding of the events in the micro and macro text in a unique way, appropriate to his/her level, is also an important factor. The author of the text necessarily takes these factors into account in the creative process. Compared to works of fiction, integration is easier to detect in scientific works. In texts of this type, the category of continuum (continuous flow of information) comes to the fore.

Integration in literary texts manifests itself both within the syntactic whole and between these syntactic wholes. The following are considered to be the common features of integration in both cases:

- 2) meaning integration expressed in the integrity of the subject;

- 3) communicative integration, in which each subsequent element (sentences in a syntactic whole, syntactic wholes in a complex syntactic whole) arises by referring to the previous one;

- 4) structural integration using anaphoric pronouns, pronoun-adverbs and other linguistic means.

We have already noted that integration itself is a process. This process involves the selection of more significant parts of the text for the content of conceptual information. In the creative act reflected in the text, an abundance of information or excessive detail referring to the main content may also manifest itself. Often, the listener or reader does not take these elements into account. The main and secondary semantic relations in the text, that is, the meaning accents between individual semantic utterances, are among the factors that lead to the emergence of integration. [20].

The integration of a literary text implies the repeated reading of this work. Moreover, a new point of view appears each time in the process of this reading. After the analysis of stylistic devices in the procedures that ensure the integration of the text and the semantic connection that unites all elements, connects individual parts, and covers the entire content, an idea of the integrity of the work is formed.

There are many commonalities between the category of integration and the category of cohesion of the text, which appear at first glance. Both categories are conditioned by repetitions, pronouns, various verb forms, substitution with synonyms, anaphoric, nominative chain means. There are also significant differences between these two categories. First of all, as I. R. Galperin said, cohesion should be perceived as a formal-logical category, and integration as a psychological category. In the other words, while cohesion is carried out by formal-structural means, the integration of the text depends on the associative situation. This category is understood when approaching a work of art analytically. Since a work of art is created for the reader (communicant), and the information in the work is intended directly for him, a two-way relationship is formed in the reading process: the author and the reader (listener). The understanding of the work as a whole, that is, the disclosure of the author's thought, the per-

ception of the idea of the work depends on the life experience of the reader (listener), his literary erudition, taste, his attitude to the read artistic material, and finally his mood. In the realization of all this, the integrative nature of the work plays a key role. [17].

Conclusion:

Cohesion, as we have shown in the previous sections, is a form of communication using grammatical, semantic and lexical means. These forms connect the individual parts of the text together. Integration, on the other hand, unites all its parts to ensure the integrity of the text. Although integration is realized in some cases by means of cohesion, in other cases it is realized in associative relations. In texts that are not large in volume, especially neutral (i.e., non-fiction), cohesion provides complete integration. Cohesion is realized intermittently, piecemeal in syntactic wholes. Integration is a continuous process, and this process complements each other in syntactic wholes, and is realized sequentially in waves.

In fiction texts, cohesion plays an auxiliary role in small parts, and is not easily noticeable due to the connection between large parts. Since judgment in fiction is carried out figuratively, indirectly, the integration process is complicated, and to understand this process, as we said above, analytical thinking is required, capable of making sense of implicit connections.

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